

DIGITAL ASSISTANCE IN THE MODERN AGE: GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS' IMPACT ON BACHELOR OF SECONDARY EDUCATION STUDENTS' PERSONALIZED LEARNING

Sanggalo, Maybelyn C.¹, Pacada, Sherene R.², & Mercado, Jazlien Mae M.³

¹Department of Teacher Education, Cavite State University CCAT Campus, Rosario, Cavite, Philippines

*Correspondence: ¹maybelyn.sanggalo@cvsu.edu.ph, ²sherene.pacada@cvsu.edu.ph,

³jazlienmae.mercado@cvsu.edu.ph

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to comprehensively examine the impact of generative AI tools on the personalized learning of second and third year Bachelor of Secondary Education students majoring in Science, Mathematics, and English at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus. A descriptive-correlational research design was used, and data were collected from 110 students through a validated survey questionnaire measuring AI usage, learning autonomy, academic performance, and personalized learning experiences. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data and determine relationships among variables. Findings revealed that generative AI tools significantly supported personalized learning across all measured domains, with AI usage significantly above baseline for academic performance ($t = 54.99$, $df = 109$, $p < .001$), learning autonomy ($t = 50.13$, $df = 109$, $p < .001$), and student engagement ($t = 44.05$, $df = 109$, $p < .001$). Significant positive relationships were also observed among the variables: academic performance and learning autonomy ($r = 0.557$, $p < .001$), academic performance and student engagement ($r = 0.372$, $p < .001$), and learning autonomy and student engagement ($r = 0.340$, $p < .001$). These results suggest that generative AI tools enhance personalized learning by fostering autonomy and engagement, thereby improving academic outcomes, and provide practical recommendations for responsible and effective AI use among BSEd students.

Keywords: *Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI), Personalized Learning, Bachelor of Secondary Education (BsED), Learning Autonomy, Academic Performance, Student Engagement*

1. Introduction

Generative artificial intelligence is one of the results of innovation. As the technology evolves, generative artificial intelligence tools are increasingly being integrated into education, leading to a major transformation altering not only how students learn and study, but also how they experience learning itself. These tools allow students to receive instant explanations, personalized feedback, and learning support tailored to their pace and preferences, which may strengthen their personalized learning experience (Campos, 2025; Haleem et al., 2022). However, despite the growing use of generative AI in higher education, little is known about how it truly affects students' learning behaviors, whether it encourages deeper understanding or leads to dependence on automated assistance (Villareal et al., 2023). Given this uncertainty, using these tools can have both positive and negative impacts. That is why it is important to examine how they influence students'

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learning, especially now that they are becoming part of students' routines and academic practices.

Artificial intelligence in the classroom accommodates the learning speed of the students, enabling an engaging learning and enhancing academic capabilities (Milloria et al., 2024.). Prior research has aimed to address the matter by investigating the impacts of AI technologies on students' educational performance habits. Alshater (2022) revealed that although AI systems including ChatGPT can help learners generate concepts and complete academic works with greater efficiency, their poor comprehension of context might result in inadequate or inaccurate outputs, thus might have an effect on students' learning outcomes. A developing concern among researchers is that the convenience provided by AI could limit opportunities for reflection, discussion, and substantive debate among the students. AI-generated responses can drive learners to absorb information passively rather than critically assess ideas (Facione, 2020, as cited in Vieriu & Petrea, 2025). According to Bećirović et al. (2025) students who have higher AI literacy are more confident when utilizing AI for academic work, yet this does not necessarily relate to improved academic performance. This indicates that reliance on AI may shape the learner's approach to educational tasks without ensuring deeper understanding. Parveen et al. (2024) showed that AI-supported tools can enhance student collaboration, feedback, and interaction, but these tools must be used cautiously in order that students' remains fully involved and do not rely on primary artificial support. These results prove that, while AI provides support for learning, researchers continue to identify uncertainty and gaps, emphasizing the need for more investigation into how generative AI affects students' personalized learning.

In recent years, a growing number of students have started using artificial intelligence tools to assist them in their learning. Despite its potential benefits, the adoption of AI in classroom settings has been slow, largely due to the significant number of teachers who remain skeptical about technology and prefer to use traditional teaching methods (Istemic et al., 2021). This may negatively affect students' learning, as many tend to rely on AI tools when they perceive their work as insufficient or inadequate (Bancoro, 2024). To address the challenges surrounding the use of generative artificial intelligence in education, it is essential to implement AI responsibly through proper guidance, awareness, and education. Students should be informed about how AI tools can enhance their learning while understanding their limitations and potential risks, such as the risks of over-reliance and the potential for inaccurate outputs. Likewise, teachers must be made aware of how AI can enhance instruction rather than replace traditional teaching methods. AI in education must be implemented in a way that supports every student fairly, prevents bias, and promotes equal opportunities for learning, ensuring that technology enhances rather than hinders equity in education (Fu & Weng, 2024). Moreover, teachers must be trained properly to be able to effectively integrate AI in their teaching. According to Tan et al. (2025), one way to enhance teaching effectiveness is to incorporate AI into teacher professional development programs. By training teachers to use AI tools effectively, educators can improve their teaching skills, support their professional growth, enhance student learning outcomes, and guide students toward responsible AI use. Promoting informed and ethical AI use ensures that generative AI empowers Bachelor of Education students, enhances personalized learning, and fosters responsible academic development.

Although numerous studies have examined the impact of AI on student learning, most have focused on broad factors such as general challenges, perceptions, and

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academic performance, without identifying the specific AI tools students use or how these tools shape their learning processes. Moreover, existing research seldom explores cognitive aspects such as learning autonomy and engagement, and often overlooks differences across academic programs, year levels, and demographic groups, limiting the applicability of their findings. Therefore, this study was important as it addressed these gaps by examining how Bachelor of Secondary Education students at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus used generative AI tools and how these tools influenced their personalized learning outcomes. By analyzing the specific platforms students rely on and how they integrate them into their academic tasks, the study provides crucial insights into both the benefits and potential challenges of AI-assisted learning. Ultimately, understanding these effects is essential for helping students use AI responsibly, guiding educators in designing effective instructional strategies, and supporting institutions in implementing generative AI in ways that meaningfully enhance personalized learning and independent thinking.

2. Methodology

The research employed a descriptive-correlational quantitative approach to examine the impact of generative AI tools on students' personalized learning. A validated survey questionnaire was used as the main data collection tool, measuring AI usage, learning autonomy, academic performance, and personalized learning experiences. This method was chosen for its effectiveness in gathering detailed information about students' experiences and how their use of AI tools relates to learning outcomes.

The design aimed to capture the respondents' perspectives regarding their use of generative AI tools and its influence on personalized learning. To enhance the validity of the questionnaire, it was reviewed and approved by the advisers and designated validators. After obtaining the necessary permissions from the school authorities, the researchers distributed the survey to a total of 110 selected 2nd- and 3rd-year Bachelor of Secondary Education students majoring in Science, Mathematics, and English at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus. Once the completed questionnaires were collected, the responses were compiled, organized, and encoded for analysis, ensuring accuracy and completeness of the data.

In the testing and evaluation phase, descriptive statistics were utilized to summarize the gathered data. Participants provided their responses through a structured survey using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree), allowing for a nuanced understanding of their experiences and perceptions. The analysis included frequency counts, mean scores, and standard deviations to interpret the level of AI usage and corresponding personalized learning outcomes. Additionally, inferential statistics, such as t-test statistics and Pearson's correlation coefficient, were employed to examine differences and relationships among variables, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of the research objectives.

The statistical treatment was done via methodical tabulation of respondents demographic profiles and their usage patterns of AI. To make the data easier to comprehend, the researchers used the grand mean method to find the average level of agreement of the participants about how AI tools have affected their personalized learning. This enabled the researchers to pinpoint the particular factors that most closely relate to the students' learning autonomy and engagement. Beyond the analysis, ethical considerations were observed throughout the study. The researchers ensured the strict

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confidentiality of all collected data, protecting the participants' personal information and maintaining their anonymity. By adhering to established ethical protocols and analyzing the data without manipulation, the study presents accurate findings that genuinely reflect the learning experiences of the BSEd students.

This methodology establishes a clear framework for investigating how generative AI tools affect personalized learning among BSEd students. Through careful design, systematic data analysis, and adherence to ethical standards, the study aimed to provide meaningful insights that can guide the effective use of AI in educational settings.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Commonly Utilized Generative AI Tools

The study began by investigating the generative AI tools most commonly used by students in the Bachelor of Secondary Education program. A total of 110 students participated, including 45 majoring in Science, 30 in Mathematics, and 35 in English. It was found that ChatGPT was the most commonly used generative AI tool among Bachelor of Secondary Education students, with Science students using it the most (mean = 0.911), followed by Mathematics (0.833) and English (0.800). Gemini was the second most frequently used tool, while Cici and other AI tools had minimal usage, particularly among Mathematics and Science students. Overall, ChatGPT was consistently preferred across all majors, indicating its dominant role in supporting student learning activities.

Table 1. Utilization of ChatGPT by Academic Major

	ChatGPT		
	English	Mathematics	Science
Valid	35	30	45
Mean	0.800	0.833	0.911
Std. Deviation	0.406	0.379	0.288
Minimum	0.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	1.000	1.000	1.000

Out of the three majors, it was revealed that Science had the highest mean value of 0.911, suggesting that students in this field used ChatGPT tools more regularly compared to their peers in Mathematics (0.833) and English (0.800). This indicated that AI adoption was more common among Science students, possibly because their courses involved complex tasks or research where AI tools are particularly helpful. English students, while still using ChatGPT, showed a slightly lower average usage, which may have been explained by the differences in the nature of their coursework or varying levels of familiarity with AI applications.

Looking at the variability of the responses, English majors were reported to show the highest standard deviation (0.406), indicating that while some students used ChatGPT frequently, others use it very little or not at all. Mathematics students also show moderate variability (0.379), whereas Science students had the lowest variation (0.288), suggesting that ChatGPT usage among them was more consistent. The minimum and maximum values for all majors ranged from 0.000 to 1.000, showing that although some students never used ChatGPT, others made full use of these tools.

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Table 2. Utilization of Gemini by Academic Major

	Gemini		
	English	Mathematics	Science
Valid	35	30	45
Missing	0	0	0
Mean	0.486	0.433	0.400
Std. Deviation	0.507	0.504	0.495
Minimum	0.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	1.000	1.000	1.000

English majors were reported to have the highest mean level of Gemini utilization (0.486), followed by Mathematics (0.433), and lastly, Science (0.400). This pattern indicated that, on average, English students used Gemini slightly more frequently than their counterparts in Mathematics and Science. Overall, the mean values suggested a moderate level of AI utilization across all majors, with only small differences observed among the three fields.

In terms of variability, differences in AI usage patterns were evident within each major. English students showed the highest standard deviation (0.507), followed closely by Mathematics (0.504), and Science (0.495), which indicated a wide range of Gemini usage frequency among students. This suggested that while some students made frequent use of AI tools, others used them minimally or not at all. Taken together, these findings showed that despite slight differences in average usage, AI utilization remained inconsistent across the three majors.

Table 3. Utilization of Cici by Academic Major

	Cici		
	English	Mathematics	Science
Valid	35	30	45
Missing	0	0	0
Mean	0.343	0.100	0.044
Std. Deviation	0.482	0.305	0.208
Minimum	0.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	1.000	1.000	1.000

Among the three majors, English students reported the highest mean level of Cici utilization (0.343), followed by Mathematics (0.100) and Science (0.044). This indicated that, on average, English students used Cici more frequently than their peers in Mathematics and Science. Overall, the mean values suggested that Cici utilization was generally low across all majors, with only minor differences observed between the groups.

Examining the variability of the responses, the English students showed the highest standard deviation (0.482), followed by Mathematics (0.305) and Science (0.208), reflecting a wider range and a more consistent Cici usage among English majors, while low usage among Science students. This suggested that while some English students

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used Cici regularly, others used it minimally or not at all. Overall, these findings indicated that Cici utilization remained generally low, with English majors showing slightly higher and more variable engagement compared to their peers in Mathematics and Science.

Table 4. Utilization of Other Generative AI Tools by Academic Major

	Others		
	English	Mathematics	Science
Valid	34	30	45
Missing	1	0	0
Mean	0.059	0.133	0.111
Std. Deviation	0.239	0.346	0.318
Minimum	0.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	1.000	1.000	1.000

Across the three majors, English students reported the highest mean utilization of other AI tools (0.059), followed by Mathematics (0.133) and Science (0.111). This indicated that, on average, students across different majors used alternative AI tools much less frequently than the main AI platforms provided, such as ChatGPT, Gemini, and Cici. Overall, the mean values suggested that the use of other AI tools was generally limited among students, with only small differences observed between majors.

Examining the diversity of the responses, Mathematics students showed the highest standard deviation (0.346), followed by Science (0.318) and English (0.239). This indicated that the frequency of using other AI tools was more varied among Mathematics students and more consistent among English students. This suggested that while some students, particularly in Mathematics and Science, actively experimented with alternative AI tools, most students either use them very little or not at all. Collectively, the results suggested that the overall utilization of other AI tools remained low, but differences in course requirements and learning tasks may have influenced how students engaged with these tools.

3.2. Level of Utilization of Generative AI Tools by Specialization

For the level of utilization, the English major students (n = 35), composed of both second and third year respondents, obtained a mean score of 28.26 with a standard deviation of 6.934, indicating a moderate level of utilization of generative AI tools with noticeable variability in usage. The scores ranged from 10.00 to 40.00, suggesting differences in the frequency and manner of AI tool usage among students.

Likewise, the students majoring in Mathematics (n = 30) attained a mean score of 27.83 with a standard deviation of 5.453, which indicated a moderate level of utilization with fairly consistent usage patterns. The minimum and maximum scores ranged from 21.00 to 39.00, suggesting that Mathematics students were more uniform in their use of AI tools in their learning activities.

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On the contrary, Science major students (n = 45), achieved the highest average score of 33.04 with a standard deviation of 6.809, showing that they utilized generative AI tools more extensively than English and Mathematics majors. The scores were between 20.00 and 49.00, indicating a broader spread of the responses.

Overall, the findings indicated that second and third year Bachelor of Secondary Education students across all majors utilized generative artificial intelligence tools in their learning activities, with Science major students exhibiting the highest level of utilization, followed by English and Mathematics majors.

Table 5. Level of Generative AI Tool Utilization among BSED Students by Major

	Level of Utilization of Gen AI Tools		
	English	Mathematics	Science
Valid	35	30	45
Missing	0	0	0
Mean	28.26	27.83	33.04
Std. Deviation	6.934	5.453	6.809
Minimum	10.00	21.00	20.00
Maximum	40.00	39.00	49.00

3.3. Use of Generative AI Tools to Support Personalized Learning

The results in this table indicated that Bachelor of Secondary Education students utilized generative AI tools to support their personalized learning across all measured domains. In the case of Academic Performance, the t-value of 54.99 (df = 109, $p < .001$) indicated that the mean usage of AI tools by students was significantly different from the baseline, suggesting consistent use to support their academic activities. Likewise, in the Learning Autonomy domain, the t-value of 50.13 (df = 109, $p < .001$) reflected that students' AI tool usage was significantly above the baseline, indicating that AI tools were employed to assist in managing their own learning and making independent study decisions. Lastly, regarding Student Engagement, the t-value of 44.05 (df = 109, $p < .001$) revealed a statistically significant difference from the baseline, showing that students consistently used AI tools in ways that supported active participation and involvement in learning activities.

In general, the findings revealed that the utilization of generative AI tools was consistently present across the three domains. The significance of the results ($p < .001$) confirmed that these usage patterns were unlikely to have occurred by chance, highlighting the important role of AI tools in supporting BSEd students' personalized learning experiences.

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Table 6. Relationship between Generative AI Usage and Student Learning Outcomes

Measure 1	Measure 2	t	df	p
Academic performance	Usage	54.99	109	< .001
Learning Autonomy	Usage	50.13	109	< .001
Student Engagement	Usage	44.05	109	< .001

3.4. Impact of Generative AI Tools on Personalized Learning

The study found a moderate and statistically significant positive relationship between academic performance and learning autonomy ($r = 0.557$, $p < .001$). This suggested that students with a greater percentage of learning autonomy performed better academically. The strong evidence of this relationship indicated that learning autonomy could have a vital role in how generative AI facilitated personalized learning. Generative AI appeared to promote self-directed learning practices that independently addressed learning gaps and translated into improved academic performance.

A weak to moderate positive relationship was found between academic performance and student engagement ($r = 0.372$, $p < .001$). Although the relationship was of moderate significance, the relationship emphasized the importance of behavioral engagement and cognitive in academic performance. These findings implied that generative AI tools may have enhanced performance by instant feedback and adaptive content, which assisted the learners to be involved in academic work.

In addition, a weak to moderate positive relationship was observed between learning autonomy and student engagement ($r = 0.340$, $p < .001$), which suggested that autonomous learners were more likely to be actively engaged in the learning process. This relationship highlights a complementary interaction between autonomy and engagement, wherein students who took ownership of their learning were more motivated to participate, explore, and persist in academic activities. In the context of generative AI, this may reflect how AI-driven tools empowered learners to make independent learning choices while simultaneously encouraging deeper engagement with instructional content.

Collectively, these data suggested that academic performance was positively associated with both learning autonomy and student engagement in AI-assisted personalized learning environments. Learning autonomy and engagement were also positively related to each other, indicating interconnected factors that support student outcomes. While the correlational nature of the findings does not imply causation, the consistent significance across all relationships supports the role of generative AI tools in fostering meaningful learning experiences. By promoting autonomy and engagement, AI technologies indirectly contributed to improved academic performance, offering practical guidance for educators seeking to cultivate motivated, independent, and academically successful learners.

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Table 7. Association among Student Learning Outcomes

		Pearson's r	p
Academic performance	Learning Autonomy	0.557	< .001
Learning Autonomy	Student Engagement	0.340	< .001
Student Engagement	Academic Performance	0.372	< .001

3.5. Summary of Findings

The overall finding of the study showed that generative AI tools were actively integrated into the learning practices of Bachelor of Secondary Education students, with clear patterns emerging across majors and learning outcomes. ChatGPT was identified as the most commonly utilized tool, recording the highest mean usage among Science students (M = 0.911), followed by Mathematics (M = 0.833) and English (M = 0.800), indicating its consistent and dominant role in supporting academic tasks. Gemini showed moderate utilization, while Cici and other AI tools were generally used at low levels, particularly among Mathematics and Science students. In terms of overall utilization, Science majors demonstrated the highest level of generative AI use (M = 33.04), surpassing English (M = 28.26) and Mathematics students (M = 27.83), suggesting a greater reliance on AI tools in science-related coursework.

Furthermore, the t-test results revealed that students consistently used generative AI tools to support academic performance (t = 54.99, p < .001), learning autonomy (t = 50.13, p < .001), and student engagement (t = 44.05, p < .001), meaning that AI usage in these areas was significantly higher than the baseline and unlikely to have occurred by chance. These results indicate that students actively relied on AI tools not only to improve academic outcomes but also to manage their own learning and remain engaged in academic tasks. Consistent with these findings, significant positive relationships were observed among academic performance, learning autonomy (r = 0.557, p < .001), and student engagement (r = 0.372, p < .001), indicating that students who were more autonomous and engaged tended to perform better academically. Overall, the data suggested that generative AI tools supported personalized learning by fostering greater autonomy and engagement, which were closely associated with improved academic performance among BSEd students.

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

This study concludes that generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools, such as ChatGPT, Gemini, and Cici, have become important academic supports for Cavite State University-CCAT Campus Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) students. The research shows that these tools are used by students across all majors, with Science students using them the most, followed by English and Mathematics students. This demonstrates that using generative AI has a clear positive effect on students' personalized learning, including their academic performance, learning independence, and engagement.

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In particular, the findings further reveal that these tools help students understand difficult lessons by reducing cognitive load and simplifying complex concepts, allowing them to better grasp and remember the material. Hence, students can cope with their lessons even if they learn at different speeds or have different learning needs, ensuring that no one is left behind. Therefore, generative AI supports learning autonomy by acting as a personal guide, letting students study at their own pace and make independent decisions about their study habits. In addition, AI-assisted learning increases student engagement by encouraging them to participate actively and become more involved in their academic tasks. To sum up, the research indicates that these tools significantly improve personalized learning; however, students still need to balance AI use with their own critical thinking skills so that they do not get overly reliant on automated help.

While this study shed light on the generative AI tools in personalized learning among Bachelor of Secondary Education students, it also identifies various topics that require further investigation. To fill the gaps and build on the current findings the future researcher should take the following directions:

The study focused on the cognitive aspect of learning, such as academic success, learning autonomy, and student engagement. It does not investigate students' emotional, and behavioral responses when using generative AI tools. Future research could concentrate on students' emotional experiences such as motivation, anxiety, and dependency among second-year and third-years of Bachelor of Secondary Education.

The research did not consider the social implications of AI integration in educational settings. Specifically, the impact of generative AI on collaboration learning, peer interaction, and student-teacher interaction. The future research could look into how generative AI influences classroom dynamics.

The study is limited to second-year and third-year Bachelor of Secondary Education students specializing in English, Mathematics, and Science. It excluded first-year and fourth-year students, as well other specializations. The future research could look into the experience of freshmen who were adjusting to higher education or senior students who were engaged in internships.

The study included students' answers and did not consider the perception, readiness, and concerns of faculty members regarding AI integration in instructions, it might help to investigate the teacher perspectives about generative AI such as level of acceptance, skepticism, ethical boundaries, and willingness to include AI tools into teacher education curriculum for future study.

This study was conducted in a short time frame, as a result, long-term learning outcomes and retention were not tested; therefore, future research may look into whether AI-assisted learning helps to sustain understanding and skill development over time. Furthermore, while the research paper advocated the creation of institutional policies on AI usage, it did not conduct direct assessment of efficiency of existing ethical principles, data privacy measures, and governance structures, suggesting that the future could focus on analyzing ethical government models for AI application in higher education organizations.

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